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1772 Guugu Yimidhir

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I. Phonotactics

- word initially: only stops, nasals, semi-vowels
- word finally: only lateral, rhotics, semi-vowels, /ŋ/ (apico-alveolar), /ŋ/ (lamino-dental)
- most roots are disyllabic and begin with a C (except two particles) but can end in a V

root structure:

$C^1V^1(C^2V^2)^x (C^3) \quad x \geq 0$

C¹, C³ - single consonants

C² - either a single C (any) or a cluster of up to three consonants (either homorganic nasal+stop or any possible final C+following bilabial/velar stop/nasal or a following bilabial/velar homorganic nasal-stop cluster)

- few monosyllabic roots
- all monosyllabic fullwords have long vowels
- the only monosyllabics with short vowels are unstressed clitic particles
- few monosyllabic particles - these have long V and / or a final C
ex.: bu:r 'nest'
- demonstratives and english loans are open monosyllabics
ex.: di: 'tea'

Clusters

- non-nasal sonorants (y, w, l, r, ɾ) do not occur as final elements in a medial cluster within roots, except: reduplicated forms of verbs with medial /w/ occasionally exhibit clusters which violate this rule
- no geminate clusters
- same possibilities governing medial clusters also apply across morpheme boundaries
- through morphological processes (especially verbal reduplication) clusters can be produced which do not follow these restriction
these clusters are reduced in the speech of elder people to adjust them according to the rules:

- when /r/ combines with an apical C, /r/ is dropped
ex.: wunlungur 'thunder' + -ŋda 'ERG' > wulungu-ŋda
- when /l/ meets an apical C or cluster the resulting form undergoes a kind of "retroflexization"
ex.: guṅḍal 'hit' > red.: *[guṅḍa:lṅḍal] but [guṅḍa:ɽṅḍal]
wa:ḍal 'say' > red.: *[wa:ḍa:lḍal] but [wa:ḍa:ɽal]

II. Phonological Processes

i. Lengthening and Shortening across morpheme boundaries (stem-suffix)

disyllabic stem C¹V¹C²V²(C³) can combine with 3 types of suffixes:

- ordinary suffix: cause V² to be long unless C³ is null or a nasal (/ŋ/ or /ŋ/)
- lengthening suffix: cause V² to be long though not if C³ is a nasal
- shortening suffix: shortens second syllable: C¹V¹C²V²:C³ > C¹V¹C²V²C³

These sorts of behaviour characterize all inflectional and derivational suffixes while length on monosyllable and trisyllables is not affected.

These processes apply only to stem-affix boundaries but not between words:

Ex.: ṅambal 'stone'

ṅulu ṅamba:l-ḍir
3.SG.NOM money-COM

'He has money'

ḍagu ṅambal dyi (/dy/ lamino-palatal)
thing.ABS money.ABS really

'That's really money!'

Compounding Processes do not engender lengthening.

ii. Retroflexization

medial clusters of l+apical stop/nasal/cluster produced by morphological processes change according to:

lḍ > ɽ

lṅ > ɽṅ

lṅḍ > ɽṅḍ

- retroflexization of word-final /r/

iii. glide insertion

between stem final laminal nasal and any C-initial suffix

ex.: ḍawu:ṅ + -ngu 'PURP' > ḍawu:yṅ -ngu 'for a friend'

iv. assimilation of stem final laminal nasal

ṅ+g > ṅg

v. Dropping:

a) Reduction of geminate clusters

clusters of identical consonants can be produced by morphological processes and are reduced to a simple C

b) /-iy/ in word final position or before a consonant is reduced to /i/

III. Stress

- close relationship with length: long vowels always bear stress

- disyllabic in which neither vowel is long: 'ᵒᵒ

ex.: 'ᵒambal 'stone, money'

- words with more than 2 syllables and no long V: primary stress on the first ᵒ, secondary stress on all odd-numbered syllables

ex.: 'marbuᵒgan 'cave'

- monosyllables with short vowels = unstresses clitic particles (seem never to be pronounced as independent words)

- words containing a long vowel:

- long V in first syllable and short Vs in the remaining follow the same stress pattern as above: 'ᵒᵒ

- long V in the second syllable: ᵒᵒ; ex.: ma'gi:l ,branch'

- long V in both syllables: 'ᵒᵒ (equal stress); ex.: 'bu:'ra:y 'water'

- long vowels are not found after the 2nd syllable except on certain compounds, but the rhythm of secondary stress set up in the first two syllables of a word continues onto third and subsequent syllables produced by suffixation

--> 3 patterns:

1. if first two syllables 'ᵒᵒ, secondary stress on all odd-numbered syllables

ex.: 'marbuᵒgaᵒ-bi-gu 'still in the cave'

2. if first two syllables ᵒᵒ, secondary stress on all even-numbered syllables

ex.: ma'gi:l-ᵒgay-gu 'just branches'

3. if first two syllables 'ᵒᵒ, following syllable begins with pattern of secondary stress falling on all odd-numbered syllables

ex.: 'bu:'ra:y-bi-gu 'still in the water'

- phrase stress or emphasis occasionally alter these patterns

- vowel length is altered by many inflectional and derivational processes (see II.i.)

IV. Reduplication

i. nominal reduplication

- neither form nor meaning seems to be regular

- limited to a few words

- often plural meaning
- cited examples are total reduplication
- ex.: gabi:r 'girl' > gabi:r= gabi:r 'girls'

ii. adjective reduplication

- first two syllables added to the beginning of the simple stem
- intensity, repetition
- ex.: yimi-ḍir 'this way' > yimi=yimi-ḍir 'this same way, again'

iii. verbal reduplication

- meaning: repeated or continuous action in progress, or an action done to excess
- involved are the last two syllables of the verb stem having the form:

$(C^1V^1(L)[N/\emptyset])C^2V^2$ (L – non-nasal sonorant)
 1 2 3 4 5 6

reduplicated stem is formed by adding a syllable of the form:

$l[N'/\emptyset]C^2V^2$

N' – homorganic nasal conditioned by the following C² and where the presence or absence is conditioned by the presence or absence of a nasal in position 4 of the original stem

- resulting reduplicated stem:

$(C^1V^1(L)[N/\emptyset])C^2V^2l[N'/\emptyset]C^2V^2$
 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

regular phonological rules apply to the string: lengthening rule:

unless segment 9 is a member of L lengthen segment 6

ex.: waṛmba 'return' > waṛmba:lmba 'returning'

123456

yu:li 'stand' > yu: li li 'standing'

1256

12 56 910

applies to almost all verbs; exception of a certain conjugation: along 3 patterns:

- for stems $C^1V^1(V^1)(L)C^2V^2(V^2)$ -

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

1. if C² is an apical or laminal stop (segment 4 is either null or y), the reduplicated stem is formed by deleting segment 7 and adding a syllable of the form C²V²:

$C^1V^1(V^1)(y)C^2V^2C^2V^2$

Ex.: bayd'ia 'cover' > bayd'ia:dia 'covering' (/d/ lamino-palatal)

2. applies to stems except when segment 5 is /d/, /d/ or /d/:

to the shortened unreduplicated stem, this pattern adds segments /ɿC²V²/:

$C^1V^1(V^1)(L)C^2V^2ɿC^2V^2$

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

- clusters at 7 and 8 will reduce by deleting segment 8 if it is a member of L

- if segment 8 is not deleted then by a lengthening rule for reduplication segment 6 is lengthened

ex.: daga-ʁ 'grow' > daga:ʁga-ʁ 'growing'

- for stems with a medial nasal: C¹V¹(V¹)NV²(V²)- > red.: + -nNV²

or stems C¹V¹(V¹)NC²V²(V²)- > red.: + -nC²V²

C¹V¹(V¹)(N)C²V²nC²V²

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9